

Synthesis of Some Bifunctional Tetradentate Aldimine Derivatives of Germanium(IV)

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The reactions of ethylorthogermanate with the bifunctional tetradentate aldimines derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and diamines have been studied and derivatives of the type $\text{Ge}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4(\text{SB})$ (where SBH_2 represents the aldimine molecule) have been isolated. The exchange reactions of these derivatives with 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol have also been carried out. The ultraviolet, infrared and proton magnetic resonance spectra of these derivatives have been recorded and their molecular weights determined ebullioscopically in chloroform. These were found to be non-electrolytes in anhydrous DMF.

A brief survey of the literature revealed extensive studies on the Schiff base complexes of transition elements and in recent years even derivatives of nontransition elements are receiving attention. Among the IV group elements, Schiff base complexes of $\text{Si}(\text{IV})^{1-4}$, $\text{Sn}(\text{IV})^{5-9}$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{IV})^{10}$ have been largely investigated and the literature records only a few studies on similar derivatives of the remaining members. Reactions of ethylorthogermanate with bidentate and tridentate aldimines have been reported^{11,12}. However, reactions of ethylorthogermanate with the bifunctional tetradentate aldimines do not seem to have been studied so far. The present paper reports the synthesis of germanium(IV) complexes of bifunctional tetradentate aldimines obtained by the condensation of ethylenediamine, 1,2-propylenediamine or 1,3-propylenediamine with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde. The resulting new products have been isolated in almost quantitatively yields.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Benzene (B. D. H., A. R.) was dried by refluxing over sodium wire for several hours and finally distilled azeotropically with ethanol. Absolute alcohol was dried by refluxing over calcium oxide (anhydrous), sodium and magnesium wires respectively for several hours and finally distilled azeotropically with benzene. Ethylorthogermanate was prepared by the ammonia method¹³. It was distilled at 80°/9.0 mm before use and then analyzed :

Found : Ge, 28.69 ; OC_2H_5 , 71.01
Calcd. for : $\text{Ge}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$: Ge, 28.71 ; OC_2H_5 , 71.29%

The Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with the

appropriate diamine in absolute alcohol and then recrystallized.

All glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable joints was used, special precautions being taken to exclude moisture. The fractionations were carried out on a column packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total-condensation variable take-off still head. Molecular weights were determined in boiling chloroform by means of a semi-micro ebulliometer (GallenKamp) using thermister sensing.

Analytical :

Germanium was determined as germanium dioxide and nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method. Ethanol was estimated by oxidation with normal $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in 12.5% sulphuric acid. The IR spectra were recorded in the range of 4000-200 cm^{-1} with a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating infrared spectrophotometer and PMR spectra in CDCl_3 on a Perkin-Elmer RB-12 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. The absorption spectra measurements of the solutions of aldimines and their germanium complexes in chloroform have been carried out with a Toshniwal spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cell in the region 600-240 nm. Conductivity measurements were carried out by conductivity bridge type 235 (ANUVIDYUT, ROORKEE) and the melting points determined in sealed tubes.

Reactions :

The reactions of ethylorthogermanate and the aldimines in 1 : 1 molar ratio were carried out in anhydrous benzene. The reaction mixture was then refluxed with the slow fractionation of ethanol-benzene azeotrope till the boiling temperature of benzene was reached and the liberated ethanol was estimated. The products were rendered free from solvent under reduced pressure and the resulting

TABLE 1—SYNTHESES, ANALYSES AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF GERMANIUM COMPLEXES

Ge(OC ₂ H ₅) ₄ (g)	Schiff base (g)	Refluxing time (hrs)	Product, Yield (g) and characteristics	Ethanol in the Azeotrope (g) Found (Calcd.)	Analysis(%)		Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
					Ge Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Cal d.)	
1.01	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ (1.08)	12	Ge(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂), (1.50), Yellow, solid, insoluble in benzene, melts at 271°C	0.36 (0.37)	17.00 (16.91)	6.55 (6.53)	440 (429)
0.85	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ (0.70)	14	Ge(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂), (1.00), Brownish yellow, solid, sparingly soluble in benzene, decomposes at 220°C	0.30 (0.31)	19.49 (19.56)	7.38 (7.55)	378 (371)
1.68	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ * (1.39)	12	Ge(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂)*, (2.01), yellow, foamy solid, soluble in benzene melts at 132°C	0.60 (0.61)	19.70 (19.56)	7.50 (7.55)	367 (371)

* has been used to distinguish between the compounds of the same molecular formula.

TABLE 2—SYNTHESES, ANALYSES AND PROPERTIES OF Ge(C₆H₁₂O₂)(SB) TYPE OF COMPLEXES

Compound (g)	C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ (g)	Refluxing time (hrs)	Product, Yield (g) and characteristics	Ethanol in the azeotrope (g) Found (Calcd.)	Analysis%		Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
					Ge Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	
Ge(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂) (0.98)	0.26	12	Ge(C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂)(C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂), (0.95), Yellow, solid, insoluble in benzene, decomposes at 290°C	0.22 (0.21)	16.01 (15.95)	6.23 (6.15)	440 (455)
Ge(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂) (0.75)	0.23	16	Ge(C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂)(C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂), (0.66), Brown, solid, soluble in benzene, decomposes above 250°C	0.18 (0.18)	18.28 (18.28)	7.00 (7.05)	405 (397)
Ge(OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂)* (1.50)	0.47	15	Ge(C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₂)(C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂)* (1.40), Yellow, solid, soluble in benzene, melts at 245°C	0.35 (0.37)	18.35 (18.28)	7.25 (7.05)	420 (397)

derivatives were then obtained in almost quantitative yields. The experimental details of the syntheses of these derivatives are enlisted in Table 1.

Exchange reactions :

Diethoxy germanium aldimine was taken in a 100 ml R. B. Flask containing 40 ml of dry benzene and the calculated amount of 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol was added. The contents were then refluxed for 10-12 hours and the excess of the solvent was removed on the ratiohead and then under reduced pressure. The details of their syntheses, analyses and physical properties are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of ethylorthogermanate with tetradentate aldimines (SBH₂) in 1 : 1 molar ratio can be represented as follows :

With a view to prepare compounds of the type Ge(SB)₂, 1 : 2 molar reactions were also carried out

in presence of excess of aldimine, but these were found to be unsuccessful probably due to the steric factors.

The resulting compounds were obtained in the form of yellow solid and an attempt to distil some of these could not be successful. They are fairly miscible with DMF and found to be monomers in boiling chloroform. Thus the central metal atom acquires probably the coordination number six in these derivatives.

Further, the replacement reactions of Ge(OC₂H₅)₂(SB) type of derivatives with 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol can be represented by the following equation :

These are also monomeric in nature, quite soluble in chloroform and DMF and behave as non-electrolytes. However, as compared to the parent derivatives, these are quite resistant to hydrolysis and melt/decompose at higher temperatures.

Conductivity measurements :

The conductance of the newly synthesized derivatives has been determined in dimethylformamide and the results correspond to their non-electrolytic nature.

Infrared spectra :

In the case of these aldimines the stretching frequency of the hydrogen bonded OH is shifted considerably to the lower side and overlaps with the ν C-H vibration exhibiting a broad band in the region 2940-2800 cm^{-1} . Freedman¹⁴ has also reported similar absorption bands in the region 2800-2600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of N-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)salicylideneamine and N,N'-ethylene bis(salicylaldimine). These bands completely disappear on chelation of the germanium to oxygen.

A band of strong intensity is observed in the 1635-1620 cm^{-1} region in the spectra of Schiff bases and this may be attributed to ν C=N overlapping with hydrogen bonded ν C=O. However, in the germanium complexes, this is slightly shifted to the higher frequency side and this probably indicates the coordination of germanium to nitrogen¹⁵ as well as oxygen. A strong band at around 1060 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the $\sqrt{\text{Ge}-\text{O}-\text{C}}$ vibrations¹⁶.

The maximum intensity bands in the Schiff base complexes in the regions 900-870 and 700-680 cm^{-1} are due to $\sqrt{\text{Ge}-\text{O}^{15}}$ and $\sqrt{\text{Ge}-\text{N}^{17}}$ respectively.

Proton magnetic resonance spectra :

The ¹HNMR spectra of N,N'-ethylene bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldimine) and its 1:1 germanium complex have been recorded in CDCl_3 . The 14.60 δ peak due to hydrogen bonded NH protons of the ligand disappears in the corresponding germanium compound indicating chelating nature of the aldimine.

The proton signal for methylene protons at 8.82 δ in aldimine shifts downfield in the spectra of the germanium complex (9.35) showing their deshielding and which is possibly due to the donation of lone pair of electrons by nitrogen to the central germanium atom and resulting in the formation of a coordinate linkage. This is further supported by the fact that the signal of methine protons in the germanium complex (4.50 δ) shows considerable downfield shifting as compared to the corresponding signal in the case of Schiff base (3.80 δ).

Electronic spectra :

All these ligands possess three bands around 255, 320 and 405 nm. The bands around 255 nm and 320 nm respectively assigned to $\phi \rightarrow \phi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ benzenoid transitions¹⁸, in view of the previous assignments. The remaining third band at around 405 nm is due to the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition within the azomethine group. The comparison of the spectra of the complexes with those of ligands shows that there is no much change in the nature of the complexes except that the bands in the spectra of the complexes are broader and more intense than those of the aldimines.

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